

Defining “Maritime Security”

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Abstract:

The concept of maritime security is multi-faceted and constantly evolving to meet changing threats and challenges. While there is no universally accepted definition, it generally includes the protection of a state's maritime interests, the prevention of threats to maritime safety, and the protection of the marine environment. Common threats to maritime security include piracy, terrorism, illegal fishing, and human trafficking. However, addressing these threats is complex and difficult due to the vastness of the maritime domain, diverse stakeholders, lack of international consensus, and limited resources. Despite these challenges, maritime security is crucial to the global economy and the well-being of billions of people. It is essential that countries work together to enhance maritime security and protect the interests of all.

Keywords: Maritime security, Maritime safety, Maritime threats, Maritime challenges, Maritime non-traditional threats, UNCLOS

Introduction

Imagine the consequences if a cargo ship were to explode and block harbors for weeks without the use of a dirty bomb, in a major port. The economic impact would be staggering with estimates suggesting that a shutdown of Singapore's harbor could cost over \$200 billion annually. Additionally an attack on a loaded petrol tanker in any of the harbors would not only devastate global trade but also provide terrorists with an event comparable to 9/11, which is one of their objectives. [1] To prevent all these threats it becomes crucial to prioritize security. Maritime security plays a role in safeguarding vessels, ports and coastal areas from risks such as piracy, terrorism, smuggling, illegal fishing and other criminal activities. In India there are laws and regulations governing security. The Indian Maritime Security Act of 2002 establishes a framework to protect India's territories from terrorism smuggling operations and other unlawful activities. [2] This Act grants authority to the Indian Coast Guard and other relevant agencies for ensuring security. Furthermore the Indian Ports Act dating back to 1908 empowers the central government to enact laws pertaining to security measures including controlling operations related to smuggling prevention

well as order preservation and property protection. [3]

1. Conceptual Framework of Maritime Security

The conceptual framework of security has evolved over time due to events along, with legal precedents and international agreements. Its primary objective is not protecting vessels. Also safeguarding ports and coastal areas while addressing concerns related to national security interests, economic stability and environmental preservation. The importance of security has been heightened by incidents of piracy and naval battles. Nations have come to acknowledge the necessity of safeguarding waterways and commercial routes.

1. UNCLOS; The United Nations Convention, on the Law of the Sea (UNCLOS) [4] which was approved in 1982 governs all matters related to the oceans including security. It delineates zones such as waters, exclusive economic zones and high seas outlining both states rights and responsibilities in ocean usage and protection. UNCLOS facilitates cooperation in safeguarding security and combating illicit activities.
2. International Ship and Port Facility Security (ISPS) Code; Adopted by the

International Maritime Organization (IMO) in 2002 this code establishes fundamental security standards for ships and ports to counter threats like terrorism, smuggling and unauthorized access. It requires security planning, drills and assessments to coordinate responses to potential security risks. [5]

3. IMO Conventions; The IMO has established a number of conventions specifically addressing security concerns. One example is the Suppression of Acts Against the Safety of Maritime Navigation (SUA Convention) which aims at preventing and punishing acts of terrorism or other unlawful activities against ships. Additionally SOLAS (International Convention for the Safety of Life, at Sea) includes provisions pertaining to security. [6][7]
4. Regional Collaborations; Various regional agreements and initiatives have been implemented with the aim of enhancing security. Countries, in East Africa and the Western Indian Ocean region have come together to sign the Djibouti Code of Conduct which aims to combat piracy and armed robbery at sea. In Asia various nations cooperate through the "Regional Cooperation Agreement on Combating Piracy and Armed Robbery against Ships in Asia (ReCAAP)" to address security concerns. [8]

Maritime security holds importance for security as it plays a crucial role in maintaining a secure marine environment. It also has implications as global businesses rely heavily on marine traffic that must be protected from piracy, smuggling and other illegal activities. Furthermore environmental preservation is closely linked to security due to risks such as oil spills, illicit fishing and other threats that can harm the ecosystem. In response to incidents like the 2008 Mumbai attacks, where navigation areas were restricted by the Indian Navy and Coast Guard to prevent attacks and ensure security in affected regions efforts have been made by India and other countries to address piracy issues off Somalias coast. Naval escorts and increased patrols have proven effective in enhancing security and reducing incidents of piracy. [9]

Another notable example showcasing Indias commitment to security is the MV Alondra Rainbow case in 2003. The Indian Coast Guard successfully apprehended this

vessel near Gujarat on suspicion of transporting drugs. This operation demonstrated Indias security systems capability, in combating drug trafficking. [10]

The incident involving the MV Koyo Maru in 2002 showcased the effectiveness of Indias security and their ability to combat piracy. When armed pirates hijacked the Japanese owned vessel off the coast of Somalia the Indian Navy swiftly responded by sending INS Tabar to rescue the crew and eliminate the threat. This demonstrated Indias prowess in efforts to tackle piracy. Another crucial aspect of security is the enforcement of the International Ship and Port Facility Security Code (ISPS Code). Under this code member countries of the International Maritime Organization (IMO) are required to enhance security measures at ports and, for ships operating within their jurisdictions. The implementation of ISPS Code has proven effective in preventing security threats and criminal activities at ports. [11]

In 2014 a maritime security issue arose from a fishing dispute between Tamil Nadu and Kerala fishermen. The conflict occurred when fishermen from one state entered another states fishing waters resulting in violence. This incident highlighted the importance of maintaining security along state borders through surveillance and strict enforcement measures. [12]

2. International Legal Instruments and Conventions on Maritime Security

Furthermore international legal instruments and conventions play a role in security law. These agreements serve as guidelines for ensuring safety and security. Notably

I. UNCLOS [13] (United Nations Convention on Law of Sea) which was signed by than 160 nations in 1982 serves as an international law governing ocean affairs. UNCLOS establishes zones, outlines nations rights and obligations concerning marine resource utilization and protection well as provides mechanisms, for dispute resolution.

International cooperation, for enhancing security commences with the United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea (UNCLOS). UNCLOS is an agreement that governs the utilization and protection of oceans. It replaced agreements and customary laws in 1982 and 1994.

The primary objectives of UNCLOS are to establish standards for ocean

governance nations rights and responsibilities in maritime zones, foster collaboration between states and ensure conservation and protection of marine ecosystems. Key provisions within include;

1. Definition of Maritime Zones; UNCLOS categorizes zones as seas, contiguous zones, exclusive economic zones (EEZs) and continental shelves. These designations determine the extent of states sovereignty, jurisdiction and resource rights over surrounding waters.
2. Freedom of Navigation and Overflight in HighSeas; UNCLOS guarantees all governments the right to navigate through waters freely. It regulates passage through seas while safeguarding navigational [14] rights.
3. Exclusive Economic Zones (EEZs); According to UNCLOS an EEZ extends up to 200 miles from a states baselines. Within this zone coastal states possess rights for exploration and exploitation of resources—both living organisms and non living resources—as well as conducting scientific research activities and ensuring environmental protection. [15]
4. Continental Shelf; UNCLOS establishes boundaries for determining the limits of a coastal states continental shelf beyond its EEZ.

These provisions form the foundation for cooperation in ensuring security by promoting responsible ocean stewardship, among nations. Coastal states possess rights, over the seabed and subsoil resources of their shelf. [16]

II. The International Ship and Port Facility Security (ISPS) Code, [17] adopted in 2002 by the International Maritime Organization (IMO) aims to address security risks and combat terrorism. It sets standards that ships and ports worldwide must adhere to encompassing measures like security planning, training and audits. The ISPS Code was established to safeguard ships and port facilities against acts of terrorism sabotage or other criminal activities.

The development of the ISPS Code was driven by concerns surrounding security after events like 9/11. Its primary objective is to promote uniformity and collaboration in security while ensuring stakeholder cooperation.

Key elements of the ISPS Code include;

1. Security Assessments; Ships and port facilities are required under the ISPS

Code to conduct evaluations of security risks and vulnerabilities. These assessments contribute to the formulation of tailored security measures for each ship or port. [18]

2. Security Plans; Shipowners and operators of port facilities must develop and implement security plans based on threat assessments. These plans encompass strategies for incident prevention, deterrence, response, as addressing aspects such, as access control, cargo handling procedures, employee identification protocols and communication systems. [19]
3. Security training and drills play a role in the implementation of the ISPS Code. The code emphasizes the need to train staff, in security practices ensuring that they are well equipped to identify and respond to threats. Additionally it is recommended to conduct drills and exercises to assess the readiness and effectiveness of security measures. [20]
4. The ISPS Code also places responsibility on governments to establish laws, regulations and oversight mechanisms for security. Governments are tasked with designating authorities to inspect and audit ships as port facilities ensuring compliance with the codes requirements. It is important to note that the ISPS Code applies not to ships but also extends its coverage to port facilities. As such both ships and port infrastructure must adhere to this code with member nations of the International Maritime Organization (IMO) being responsible for enforcing it. [21]

III. Another significant international treaty related to security is the Safety of Life at Sea (SOLAS) [22] convention adopted by IMO in 1974. SOLAS primarily focuses on safeguarding lives at sea with attention given in chapters XI I & XI II regarding security. These regulations mandate that ships have security plans in place conduct drills and promptly report any incidents that may compromise safety or security. SOLAS serves as an convention setting minimum safety requirements, for ships operating in international waters. It aims not at protecting passengers but also preventing accidents through stringent safety criteria and incorporating advancements in technology over time. SOLAS aims to provide a framework to ensure the safety of ships and

the well being of passengers and crew members. It encompasses provisions;

1. Standards, for Structure and Equipment; SOLAS outlines requirements for ship structure, stability, fire safety and lifesaving equipment. These standards ensure that vessels are designed and maintained to withstand conditions and emergencies. [23]
2. Safety Management; SOLAS mandates that ships have robust safety management systems in place to identify and mitigate risks. It emphasizes the implementation of safety plans, procedures, training programs and drills to enhance onboard safety. [24]
3. Navigation and Communication; SOLAS regulates equipment, charts, voyage planning procedures and communication systems to minimize collisions at sea and improve communication between ships and shore authorities. [25]
4. Emergency Response; SOLAS mandates that ships are equipped with fire fighting capabilities, evacuation procedures, search and rescue measures well as sufficient lifeboats, rafts and other lifesaving equipment. [26]

IV. Regional Agreements; In regions regional agreements play a crucial role in addressing maritime security challenges. An example is the

1. Djibouti Code of Conduct [27] an accord covering ship piracy and armed robbery in the Western Indian Ocean and Gulf of Aden areas. This agreement promotes security through cooperation, among nations by exchanging information and building capacity.
2. "The Regional Cooperation Agreement, on Combating Piracy and Armed Robbery against Ships in Asia, known as ReCAAP plays a role in enhancing security across Asia. It facilitates collaboration among member nations to effectively combat the menace of ship piracy and armed robbery. [28]
3. RMSI: Moving towards the Western Indian Ocean region we have initiatives and frameworks aimed at addressing piracy and ensuring stability. The Combined Maritime Forces (CMF) Maritime Security Patrol Areas (MSPA) Shared Awareness and Deconfliction (SHADE) as the Somalia Contact Group on Piracy are some examples of these

Regional Maritime Security Initiatives (RMSI). [29]

4. In 2013 the Gulf of Guinea Code of Conduct was established with the objective of suppressing piracy, armed robbery and illicit marine operations within the region. This code seeks to strengthen cooperation among West and Central African countries to effectively combat piracy and armed robbery through enhanced security. [30]
5. Moving further into the Asia Pacific region we come across the ASEAN Regional Forum (ARF). This multilateral security discourse platform has actively addressed security concerns through communication, cooperation and confidence building among participating nations.
6. Lastly we have organizations known as RFMOs that're responsible for managing fisheries resources while combating illicit activities such, as unreported or unregulated fishing. The Indian Ocean Tuna Commission (IOTC) and Northwest Atlantic Fisheries Organization (NAFO) are examples that promote fishing practices alongside ensuring marine security in their respective regions." [31]
7. During Operation Ocean Shield the North Atlantic Treaty Organization (NATO) had the objective of countering piracy and ensuring security, along the coast of Somalia. Through patrols coordination efforts and intelligence sharing they successfully deterred pirate attacks. Safeguarded vulnerable vessels. [32]

3. Threats and Challenges to Maritime Security

Various factors pose risks to safety, including piracy, armed robbery, marine terrorism, illicit fishing, human trafficking, drug smuggling and environmental concerns. Addressing these issues requires an examination of both national laws that aim to combat these dangers. It is important to note that major ports in South and East Asia such as Kobe, Tokyo Yokohama Pusan Shanghai Kaohsiung Hong Kong Singapore may be targeted by terrorists due to their significance. Additionally mega ports like Los Angeles in the United States or Rotterdam in Europe can also be targets for activities. [33]

The "UN Convention on the Law of the Sea" (UNCLOS) serves as a framework for addressing maritime issues. UNCLOS establishes. Responsibilities concerning ocean usage and management among states. In

order to ensure security effectively; laws pertaining to piracy suppression, prevention of illicit activities at sea well as preservation of marine environment are crucial. Numerous international treaties and agreements have been established with a focus on enhancing security; for instance SOLAS which regulates safety including measures, against terrorism. The issue of terrorism and maritime crimes is addressed by two conventions; the "International Convention, for the Suppression of Acts of Nuclear Terrorism" and the "International Convention for the Suppression of Unlawful Acts against the Safety of Maritime Navigation." Each country has its set of laws regarding security, which encompass various offenses such as piracy, armed robbery, smuggling, trafficking and environmental protection. In India for instance they have enacted the "Suppression of Acts against Safety of Marine Navigation and Fixed Platforms on Continental Shelf Act, 2002" to combat acts of terrorism in marine navigation. The jurisdiction for addressing security concerns and issues depends on laws and circumstances. It is the responsibility of authorities in ratified states to enforce laws and treaties related to maritime crimes. Prosecution for these crimes can be carried out by states, flag states (where a vessel is registered) or states where an offense has taken place. Notably there have been developments in combating piracy in the Indian Ocean due to collaboration among Singapore, Malaysia and Indonesia in recent years. Thanks to their increased efforts and cooperation, with states piracy incidents have significantly decreased. The coordinated efforts of Indonesia, Malaysia, Singapore and Thailand, in conducting air and sea surveillance operations known as "Eye in the Sky" and Malacca Strait Patrols involve information sharing. They have also sought assistance from India, the US and Japan. [34] There are challenges in maritime security that include;

1. Piracy; In order to address piracy as a threat to security Indian legislation introduced the "Suppression of Acts against the Safety of Maritime Navigation (SUA) Act 2002". Section 3(2)(d) [35] of this act defines piracy and prescribes punishments for it. The Supreme Court case of Republic Of Italy Thr. Ambassador... Vs Union Of India & Ors established that Section 3(2)(d) makes

piracy a cognizable and non bailable offense. [36]

2. Armed Robbery; Maritime security is also threatened by robbery at sea. Different jurisdictions often categorize robbery under piracy or general criminal statutes. In India armed robbery at sea is covered by the SUA Act, 2002 as the Indian Penal Code. [37]
3. Maritime Terrorism; Addressing terrorism is a focus area for international efforts. The SUA Convention and its 2005 Protocol specifically deal with terrorism offenses. In the case United States v Hasan (2014) [38] the Eastern District of Virginia successfully convicted a pirate, under the SUA Act for acts of piracy and related offenses.

If a super tanker were to sink in the Strait of Malacca it would disrupt commerce. Force ships to take a route through the Indonesian Sunda and Flores passage. This diversion would add a 1,000 kilometers and two more days at sea resulting in an expense increase of \$8 billion. [39]

4. One major concern, for security is fishing, which involves activities that go against regulations and are not reported. To combat this issue the 1995 UN Fish Stocks Agreement plays a role. While there are currently no specific case laws on fishing individual countries have their laws and regulations in place.

Human trafficking is another challenge when it comes to security. The 2000 UN Convention against Transnational Organized Crime along with its Protocol to Prevent, Suppress and Punish Trafficking in Persons (Women and Children) addresses this problem. In India, the Prevention of Immoral Trafficking Act (PITA) from 1986 [41] specifically focuses on combating trafficking.

Drug smuggling is also a concern that needs attention for security. The 1988 UN Convention against Illicit Traffic in Drugs and Psychotropic Substances plays a role in combating drug smuggling globally. In India the NDPS Act from 1985 covers drug smuggling offenses. The Supreme Court of India has ruled that the strict liability principle applies to NDPS Act offenses in the case of State of Gujarat, v. Mohanlal Jitmalji Porwal. [42]

To effectively address security threats and issues it is essential to evaluate both national legal frameworks. The challenges related to safety and security are effectively

addressed through a combination of regulations international rules such, as UNCLOS and specific treaties. When it comes to enforcing these regulations the jurisdiction is determined based on the issue at hand involving the states with coastlines, flags and those responsible for any offenses.

4. Regarding security states have responsibilities and responses.

These include taking measures and responding to threats in their waters exclusive economic zones (EEZs) and international waters. These duties are imposed by conventions, national legislation and customary international law. [43]

States have an obligation to combat security threats such as piracy, armed robbery, terrorism illicit fishing activities, human trafficking and drug smuggling. Their responsibility for maintaining law and order along coastlines as ensuring maritime safety and security is outlined in international law.

Collaboration among states is crucial in addressing marine security threats. This collaboration can involve exchanging intelligence information conducting patrols at sea extradition procedures when necessary and providing aid. Both UNCLOS and regional agreements emphasize the importance of state cooperation to enhance security. [44]

States have the authority to prosecute offenses committed within their waters or against their vessels. This includes acts of piracy committed by their nationals on the seas or in territorial waters. International collaboration in detecting and prosecuting organized crime related to security is facilitated by instruments like the UN Convention, against Transnational Organized Crime and its Protocols. [45] In some cases states may establish courts or tribunals dedicated to handling matters of security. [46] The International Tribunal, for the Law of the Sea (ITLOS) deals with disputes concerning the interpretation and application of UNCLOS.

When it comes to their waters, exclusive economic zones (EEZs) and high seas states have responsibilities in terms of maritime security. These responsibilities include prevention, cooperation with states sharing information and carrying out prosecutions. Maritime security issues are handled by international conventions to ensure safety and security at sea. Any state

has the right to establish a tribunal for the trial of cases related to activities.

Conclusion

Maritime security plays a role in safeguarding ships, ports and coastlines against piracy, terrorism, smuggling, illegal fishing and other unlawful activities. In India specifically laws such as the Indian Maritime Security Act, Indian Ports Act and Suppression of Acts Against the Safety of Maritime Navigation and Fixed Platforms on the Continental Shelf Act are in place to maintain security. These laws empower authorities to defend territories and preserve safety.

There are legal instruments and treaties that impact marine security. UNCLOS governs ocean usage as protection measures with a focus on maritime security. The International Maritime Organization (IMO)s ISPS Code provides requirements for ship and port security to prevent terrorism and smuggling. The SOLAS convention addresses marine safety concerns including aspects related to security.

Furthermore regional agreements like the Djibouti Code of Conduct along with initiatives such as ReCAAP contribute towards enhancing security, within regions. Maritime security poses a range of challenges, including piracy, armed robbery, maritime terrorism, illegal fishing, human trafficking and drug smuggling. These issues are tackled through a combination of national laws. The jurisdiction, for prosecuting these crimes depends on factors such as the location of the offense the flag state of the vessel involved and the power of the state.

To ensure safety states have a responsibility to prevent and respond to threats within their waters, exclusive economic zones and high seas. This requires cooperation between nations in terms of intelligence sharing and joint operations. International conventions play a role in securing vessels, ports, areas while safeguarding national security interests and economic well being. Additionally protecting the environment is also a part of maritime security efforts.

In order to effectively address these challenges it is essential that countries have laws in place along, with active international collaboration and regional initiatives.

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